

1st CONFERENCE:
GUIDELINES FOR ACHIEVING
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC
GROWTH IN THE DIGITAL
ECONOMY

СТРАТЕГИЯ
УЗБЕКИСТАН
2030

ФОРУМ
2nd CONFERENCE:
GREEN ACCOUNTING AND
DIGITALIZATION
AS THE NEWEST VECTORS OF
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC
DEVELOPMENT

2nd FORUM OF
DEVELOPMENT
STRATEGY:
GLOBAL AND
NATIONAL
ECONOMIC
TRENDS

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

17-18
OCTOBER
2024

<https://strategy2024.tsue.uz/>

CONFERENCE
"ICFDS"

2030 | «UZBEKISTAN»
STRATEGY

GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI:
"O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI CONFERENCE

Macroeconomic stability
Human capital and
population welfare
World economy and
international economic
relations
Industry 4.0
International business and
international tourism
Social studies
Digital government
Artificial intelligence
and digital technologies
Digital transformation
Digital technologies
Quantitative measurement
Economic growth

17-18
OCTOBER

2024 TRENDS

GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS: "UZBEKISTAN-2030" STRATEGY

CONFERENCE ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ
"IFRS" ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ:
СТРАТЕГИЯ «УЗБЕКИСТАН -2030»

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT

GREEN ECONOMY AND DEVELOPMENT ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА И РАЗВИТИЕ

ILMIY ELEKTRON JURNAL

2024
MAXSUS SON

strategy2024.ts

3rd FORUM OF
DEVELOPMENT
STRATEGY:
GLOBAL AND
NATIONAL
ECONOMIC
TRENDS
CONFERENCE III:
NEW2AN, TRENDS
ICFDS
CONFERENCE
"IFRS" 2024

РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТISODIYOT,
АХБОРОТ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИ
ВА ТАЪЛИМНИНГ
ИСТИҚБОЛЛИ ЙУНАЛИШЛАР
"NEW2AN, ICFDS, ICDSIS"
номли параллель CONFERENCE
конференциялар "IFRS"

UZBEKISTA
STRATEGY
2030

for susta
Sustaino
sectors based on "green" corporate
accounting of digital business;
Financial management of digital business
using "green" corporate accounting;
The role of green accounting in digital
business marketing: a view from the
perspective of sustainable development;
Decarbonizing the digital economy
with a focus on green corporate
accounting and climate finance.
October 17-18, 2024

ЙУНАЛИШ: ГЛОБАЛ
ИҚТISODIYOT
РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ
ТЕНДЕНЦИЯЛАРИ ВА
ИСТИҚБОЛЛИ ЙУНАЛИШ
"Глобал ва миллий
иқтисодийот трендлари"
номли конференция

CONFERENCE III:
NEW2AN, ICFDS
TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

74-91 xalqaro daraja

ISSN: 2992-8982

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

*Elektron nashr. 452 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil
16-17-oktabrda ruxsat etildi.*

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi

Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayeich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi

Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati

Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri

Teshaboyev To'liqin Zakirovich, iqtisod fanlar doktori, professor, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti rektori

Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari

Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati

Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori

Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Infratuzilmani rivojlantirish va iqtisod ishlari bo'yicha prorektori

Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti rektori

Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, p.f.f.d., (PhD), Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya instituti rektori

Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Hududiy ta'lim muassasalari va markazlar bo'yicha prorektor v.b.

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TDIU professori

Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori

Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori

Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d., TSUE professori

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari

Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i

Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori

Musayeva Shoirazimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori

Cham Tat Huei, (PhD) USCI universiteti professori, Malayziya

Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d.,(PhD) "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d.,(PhD) TAQU katta o'qituvchisi

Djudi Smetana, p.f.n., Pittsburg davlat universiteti dosenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH

Krissi Luis, p.f.n., Pittsburg davlat universiteti dosenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH

Ali Konak (Али Кўнак), i.f.d., prof., Karabuk universiteti dosenti, Turkiya

Glazova Marina Viktorovna, i.f.n., "LUKOIL-Energoservis" Kompaniyasi iqtisodchisi, Moskva.

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., (PhD) TDIU dotsenti

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

ISSN 2992-8982

9 772992 1898002

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Oqil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjaevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Rae Kwon Chung, honorary professor of TSUE, Nobel laureate, South Korea,

Osman Mesten, member of the Turkish Parliament, head of the Turkey-Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, DSc, Prof., Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Teshaboyev Tolkin Zakirovich, doctor of economics, professor, rector of Tashkent State University of Economics

Buzrukhanov Sarvarkhan Munavvarkhanovich, DSc, Deputy Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, DSc, Prof., Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich CSc, Prof., Rector of Academy of Labor and Social Relations

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, DSc, Prof., TSUE Vice-Rector for Scientific Affairs and Innovation

Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich, DSc, Prof., TDIU Vice-Rector for Infrastructure Development and Economic Affairs

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhritdinovich, DSc, Prof., Rector of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Siddikova Sadokat Ghaforovna, PhD, Rector of the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, DSc, Prof., acting Vice-rector for regional educational institutions and centers of TSUE

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, CSc, Prof., of TSUE

Slizovsky Dimitriy Yegorovich, DSc, Prof., of the People's Friendship University of Russia

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, DSc, Prof., Rector of International "Nordic" University

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of the DGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the DCECGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganievich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Shoira Azimovna Musaeva, professor of SamDu IS Institute

Cham Tat Huei, PhD, professor at USCI University, Malaysia

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, PhD, deputy of executive director of the "El-yurt umidi" fund

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, PhD, Senior Lecturer at Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction

Judy Smetana CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Chrissy Lewis CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Ali Konak DSc, Prof., Associate Professor of Karabuk University, Turkey

Glazova Marina Viktorovna, CSc, economist at LUKOIL-Energoservis Company, Moscow.

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, associate professor of TSUE

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, doctoral student at Ankara University, Turkey

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, independent researcher of TSUE

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, p.f.f.d., (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

KBK: 65.011(50')ya43 G 55
UO'K: 330.34:005.44(575.1)(08)
ISBN: 978-9910-8817-6-3

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ
Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi
huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi
huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-son qarori bilan ro‘yxatdan
o‘tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

“Yashil” iqtisodiyotga jadal o‘tish va barqaror texnologik o‘zgarishlar provard maqsadlarimiz	12
Abduraxmonova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
Noqonuniy sigaretalar hajmini Empty pack survey hamda Gap analysis usullari yordamida aniqlash (O‘zbekiston Respublikasi misolida)	17
Sanjar Mirzaliev, Bobur Qoraboev, Surmaniso Mirzalieva	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida bank xizmat turlarini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	22
A. R. Norov, N. N. Norova	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot rivojida tijorat banklari kapitalini takomillashtirish istiqbollari	28
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich	
Ishsizlik darajasini kamaytirish yo‘lidagi strategik yondashuv: tadbirkorlikka o‘rgatish va kasbiy tayyorlash	33
Bakiyeva Iroda Akbarovna, Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich	
Meva-sabzavot mahsulotlarini eksportga yo‘naltirishda standart talablariga uyg‘unlashtirishni baholash va uni amalga oshirish yo‘llari	42
Xojiyev Elshod Yoqub o‘g‘li	
Investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda foyda solig‘idan foydalanish	50
Zarif Oripovich Axrorov	
Mamlakat iqtisodiy o‘shish va rivojlanishida xorijiy investitsiyalarning roli	55
Akishova Shaxnoza Davlet qizi	
O‘zbekiston sharoitida “yashil” iqtisodiyotni joriy etish istiqbollari: nazariya va amaliyot.....	60
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o‘g‘li	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlari faoliyatini takomillashtirish yo‘nalishlari.....	65
Sadikova Muslima Alisher qizi	
Mehnat bozorida aholi bandligini oshirishning zamonaviy usullari	70
Xuvaydullaeva Iroda Xusniddin qizi	
Ichki turizmni rivojlanlantirishning tashkiliy mexanizmining asosiy prinsiplari	76
Isomiddinov Inomjon Qurbonali o‘g‘li	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarida ichki audit jarayonlari va uning samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	79
Maxmudov A.N.	
Ishlab chiqarish resurslaridan foydalangan holda korporativ boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish	86
Karimov Akramjon Ikromjon o‘g‘li	
Kredit foiz stavkalari va unga ta‘sir etuvchi omillar tahlili.....	92
Orifova Dilnoza Obid qizi	
O‘zbekistonda hayot sug‘urtasini rivojlantirish yo‘llari	97
Jamolova Xonzoda O‘rolboy qizi	
Soliqqa Tortishning Mohiyati va Uni Iqtisodiyotdagi Ahamiyati.....	102
Ruziyev Shaxzod Behzod o‘g‘li, Togayev Salim Sobirovich	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning oziq-ovqat sanoatini rivojlantirishdagi ta‘siri	110
Abduraxmanova Zuxra Toxir qizi	
O‘zbekistonda sog‘lomlashtirish turizmini rivojlantirishda inson resurslarining o‘rni.....	115
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
Biznes jarayonlarining samaradorligini baholash ko‘rsatkichlarini muvofiqlashtirish usullari.....	121
Abdusalomova Nodira Baxodirovna	

Turizmda inson resurslarini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	126
J. Mansurov	
Hududiy turizm rivojlanishining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarini qo'llanilishi.....	131
Dustmurodov Orifjon Ismatilloevich	
Aholi ixtiyoridagi resurslarni jalb qilish orqali aholi turmush darajasini oshirish.....	138
Jo'raeva Shahlo Uchqun qizi	
Turistik xizmatlarning samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish.....	141
Abduvohidov Abdumalik Mahkamovich	
Xo'jalik subyektlarining moliyaviy salohiyatini mustahkamlash va moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashni uslubiy jihatlari.....	146
Xasanov Baxodir Akramovich, Akramov G'olibjon Bahodir o'g'li	
Mahsulot raqobatbardoshligini baholash usullari va ulardan foydalanish muammolari.....	153
Onorboev Sh.M.	
Loyihalarni Islom modeli asosida moliyalashtirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	159
Aminova Nilufar Umarboy qizi	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklarida foiz riskini boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish.....	167
Isakov Janabay Yakipbaevich	
Ayollar inson kapitalini rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	174
S.A.Bozorova, M.M.Xolmatov	
Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini yaratish bilan bog'liq loyihalarni moliyalashtirish.....	179
Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	
Effectiveness of using blockchain technologies in cash flow audit in enterprises of the republic of Uzbekistan.....	188
Atamurodov Saidmurad Yakhyoyevich	
Loan portfolio of banks in Uzbekistan and ways to improve the efficiency of loan portfolio management.....	196
Avazkhon Agzamov, Dilrabo Malikova	
Digitization of the economy and its role in enhancing bank stability and reducing poverty.....	201
Kholiyorov Murod Kahramon ugli, Kholiyorova Shokhista Kahramon kizi	
Directions for sustainable development of tourism in the namangan region of Uzbekistan.....	204
Khusniddin Egamnazarov	
Improving comprehensive monitoring of cash flows in the treasury through intelligent information fusion systems applications.....	208
Shodmonkulova Shahlo	
Importance of staff service quality at uzbek halal restaurants in Uzbekistan.....	214
Shodiyona Sanginova	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida barqaror turizmni iqtisodiy rivojlantirishda hunarmandchilikning o'rni.....	220
Xushnazarova Maxzuna Gulamdjanovna	
Mamlakat turizmini barqaror rivojlanishida mice turizmining ahamiyati.....	226
Xalimova Fayyoza Nafasovna	
Ways to expand the position of the light industrial enterprise in the yarn and knitwear market.....	231
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, Agzamov Avazkhon Talgatovich	
Improvement of methodology of accounting and analysis of included financial statements and investments in subsidiary societies.....	238
Nasirkhodjaeva Dilafruz Sabitkhanovna	

Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida investitsiyalar: barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishning muhim omili.....	254
Amonova Nazokat Utkurovna	
O'zbekiston respublikasi korxonalarida pul oqimlari auditida blokchain texnologiyalaridan foydalanish samaradorligi.....	259
Atamurodov Saidmurod Yaxyoyevich	
Iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish sharoitida o'zbekistonda turizm xizmatlar iste'molini oshirishning ekonometrik tahlili	267
Dehqonov Burxon Rustamovich	
Agrar soha korxonalarining moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlash masalalari.....	278
Erkinxojiyev I.	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarida marketing jarayonlarini tashkil etishning xorij tajribasi	283
Bazarova Fayoza Tuxtamurodovna	
Fiskal siyosatni rivojlantirishda "yashil" budjet daromadlarini o'rganish.....	287
Meyliyev O.R., Gofurova K.	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot: raqamli transformatsiyaning yashil shaharlarning iqtisodiy o'sishiga ta'siri.....	293
Xotamov Ibodulla, Najmiddinov Yahyo	
Buxoro viloyatining kichik va o'rta biznesdagi o'rni, viloyatdagi tumanlar faoliyatidan kelib chiqib hududlarni toifalarga ajratish.....	301
Bozorov Ilyos Isomiddinovich	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda ishlab chiqarishning optimal hajmi tahlili	306
Qlichev Baxtiyor Pardaevich, Xoldorov Sardor Umarovich	
Toshkent viloyati fermer xo'jaliklari faoliyatining samaradorligini tanlanma kuzatuvlar asosida statistik tadqiq etish	313
Murodov Jahongir Choriyevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida sanoat tarmog'i faoliyati samaradorligini statistik baholashning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	316
To'raeva Zilola Turg'unovna	
"Yashil" sanoat siyosati – ekologik xavfsizlikni ta'minlashning ustuvor vositasi	320
Muqimov Sherali Axmadali o'g'li	
Raqamli biznes marketingida yashil buxgalteriya hisobining roli: barqaror rivojlanish nuqtai nazaridan qarash.....	327
Allayarov Shamsiddin Amanullayevich, Iskandarov Xurshid Iskandarovich, Yoqubov Madaminbek Abdurahim o'g'li	
Fiskal barqarorlikni ta'minlashda "natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish" uslubidan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	333
Kasimova Gulyar Axmatovna, Agzamov Avazxon Talgatovich	
Регулирование занятости и управление трудовыми ресурсами в сфере туризма.....	339
Адылова Зулфия Джавдатовна, Тухтаева Хуршида Фарходовна	
Семь IPO и SPO в экономической истории узбекистана: достижения, проблемы и выводы	346
Чинкулов Кахрамон Равшанович	
Совершенствование учета затрат на производство и калькуляция себестоимости продукции	355
Омонов Шердор Ойбек угли	
Areas of effective use of marketing in the development of foreign economic relations	360
Akhmedov Ikram Akramovich	
Sanoatda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashning iqtisodiy masalalari	367
Ismoilova Gulchiroy Tolliboy qizi	

Hududlarni iqtisodiy rivojlanishida investitsiyalar ko'rsatkichi tahlili (Sirdaryo viloyati misolida)	373
Karimqulov Jasur Imomboyevich, Alimova Dilafro'z Tohir qizi	
Raqamli transformatsiya davridagi iqtisodiy o'sishga to'rtinchi sanoat inqilobining ta'siri.....	381
Mirxamidova Zahinabonu Mirxamid qizi	
Investitsion muhit va uning hududlarni iqtisodiyot va ijtimoiy rivojlanishdagi ahamiyati.....	388
Muxamadjanov Shaxriyor Solidjon o'g'li	
Portfel investisiya loyihalarini kreditlashni takomillashtirish.....	395
Ibragimov Gafurjan Axmetovich	
O'zbekistonda kapital bozorini rivojlantirish masalalari	401
Turdieva Uzayda Omirbaevna	
Korxonalarining tashqi savdo faoliyatini rivojlantirishda tijorat banklari faolligini oshirish yo'llari.....	408
Ibragimov Mansur Axmetovich	
Methodological foundations of the quality management system in construction industry enterprises.....	414
Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich, Buriyev Xakim Toshimovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirish jarayonini ekonometrik modellashtirishda xorijiy davlatlar tajribasining ahamiyati.....	419
Butanova Dilnoza Rustamovna	
O'zbekistonda qishloq turizmini rivojlantirishda Janubiy Koreya tajribasini o'rganish.....	423
Agzamova Nargiza Gapurovna	
Kimyo sanoatiga innovatsiyalarni joriy etish bo'yicha rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi.....	427
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Концептуальные основы и перспективы развития деятельности кадастровых служб республики узбекистан на основе интеллектуальных технологий	430
М.К. Валиев, А.Х. Абдуллаев, А.Р. Марахимов, Б.М. Ахмедов	
Mahalliy avtomobil benzini tarkibidagi uglevodород fraksiyalariga ekstragentlarining ta'sirini o'rganish	435
Maxmudov Muxtor Jamolovich, Murtazaev Feruzbek Ismatovich	
Oliy ta'lim muassalaridagi davlat xaridlari tizimining takomillashishi.....	441
Atamuratova Nilufar Yaxshigeldiyevna	
Tijorat banki daromadlari – moliyaviy barqarorlikning omili sifatida.....	446
Umarov Davron Shavkatovich	

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGIES IN CASH FLOW AUDIT IN ENTERPRISES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

ORCID: 0009-0002-0789-2606

Atamurodov Saidmurad Yakhyoyevich

Tashkent State University of Economics

Abstract: This article is dedicated to studying the effectiveness of using blockchain technologies in the audit of cash flows in enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The research provides a detailed analysis of the role of blockchain in enhancing transparency, ensuring data security, and automating audit processes. Based on foreign experience, the applicability of blockchain technologies in the context of Uzbekistan is examined, along with their practical outcomes and impact on financial management. Additionally, the economic efficiency of implementing blockchain technologies is discussed, and recommendations are developed for improving the regulatory environment and technological infrastructure.

Key words: cash flow audit, blockchain technologies, financial transparency, audit effectiveness, data storage, transaction monitoring, data analysis, risk identification, forecasting, automation of audit processes.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola O'zbekiston Respublikasi korxonalarida pul oqimlari auditida blokchain texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning samaradorligini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqotda blokchaining audit jarayonlarida shaffoflikni oshirish, ma'lumotlarning xavfsizligini ta'minlash va audit jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirishdagi roli batafsil tahlil qilinadi. Xorijiy tajriba asosida blokchain texnologiyalarining O'zbekiston sharoitida qo'llanish imkoniyatlari o'rganilib, ularning amaliy natijalari va moliyaviy boshqaruvga ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Shu bilan birga, blokchain texnologiyalarini joriy etishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi, me'yoriy-huquqiy muhit va texnologik infratuzilmani rivojlantirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: pul oqimlari auditi, blokchain texnologiyalari, moliyaviy shaffoflik, audit samaradorligi, ma'lumotlar saqlash, transaksiyalar kuzatuv, ma'lumotlar tahlili, xavflarni aniqlash, prognozlash, audit jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirilishi.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена изучению эффективности использования технологий блокчейн в аудите денежных потоков на предприятиях Республики Узбекистан. В исследовании подробно анализируется роль блокчейна в повышении прозрачности аудиторских процессов, обеспечении безопасности данных и автоматизации аудита. На основе зарубежного опыта рассматриваются возможности применения блокчейн-технологий в условиях Узбекистана, а также их практическое влияние на финансовое управление. Кроме того, рассматривается экономическая эффективность внедрения блокчейна, а также разрабатываются рекомендации по развитию нормативно-правовой базы и технологической инфраструктуры.

Ключевые слова: аудит денежных потоков, технологии блокчейн, финансовая прозрачность, эффективность аудита, хранение данных, мониторинг транзакций, анализ данных, идентификация рисков, прогнозирование, автоматизация аудиторских процессов.

INTRODUCTION

In an era of rapidly advancing digital technologies, the need for enterprises to improve financial management and audit processes is increasingly critical [4]. Particularly, ensuring the accurate and transparent control of cash flows and enhancing the reliability of audit processes are vital factors in maintaining the financial stability of enterprises. From this perspective, the integration of blockchain technology into audit processes has become a pressing issue.

Blockchain technology, with its fundamental principles and capabilities, has introduced a new phase in auditing practices. It is widely used to monitor cash flows, control transactions in real-time, and ensure data security. International experiences demonstrate that blockchain technology allows for the automation of audit processes, making them more transparent and reliable [3].

However, the current state of cash flow auditing in Uzbekistan's enterprises is still associated with several challenges. Issues such as ensuring the security and transparency of data and preventing the entry of incorrect financial information remain significant concerns. Blockchain technology presents a viable solution to these challenges. This article is therefore dedicated to studying the effectiveness of using blockchain technology in the audit of cash flows in enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Blockchain technology is increasingly being recognized for its potential to revolutionize financial audits, particularly in the context of cash flow management. Its primary advantages—immutability, transparency, and enhanced security—make it an ideal solution for improving audit accuracy and efficiency. According to international research, the implementation of blockchain in financial audits significantly reduces risks associated with data manipulation and fraud. Companies such as PwC and Deloitte have already started to explore how blockchain can automate audit processes, ensuring greater reliability in financial reporting.

In Uzbekistan, the adoption of blockchain technology for cash flow audits is still in its early stages. However, research conducted by local scholars indicates a growing interest in its potential. For instance, Uzbek economist A. Usmonov highlights the transformative impact of blockchain in improving the transparency and accountability of financial audits. He argues that the technology's ability to provide real-time tracking of transactions can significantly enhance the reliability of financial data and reduce the likelihood of errors and fraud. Usmonov's work emphasizes the importance of blockchain in creating an audit environment that aligns with international standards, ultimately boosting investor confidence in Uzbekistan's financial sector.

Global experiences also underscore the role of blockchain in automating various aspects of the audit process. The use of smart contracts, for instance, enables auditors to verify transactions instantly, eliminating the need for manual checks and reducing human error. This increases the overall efficiency of the audit and allows companies to focus on strategic financial management. According to research by the OECD, the application of blockchain technology in financial reporting leads to a 30% increase in audit process efficiency and significantly reduces operational costs.

In conclusion, the introduction of blockchain technology into cash flow audits in Uzbekistan offers significant benefits, including improved transparency, security, and process automation. However, as noted by both local and international scholars, the successful implementation of blockchain requires overcoming several technical, legal, and infrastructural challenges. Nonetheless, its adoption has the potential to align Uzbekistan's audit practices with global standards, fostering greater trust and integrity in the country's financial systems.

Research methodology

In the implementation of these research works, widely used methods in scientific research methodology were used. The use of deductive or inductive methods in the order from generality to individuality and vice versa is effective in studying the subject, and the method of abstract-logical thinking is important in the systematic analysis of the process. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods, in particular, observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, analysis, and synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of the research are aimed at determining the effectiveness of the use of blockchain technologies in the audit of cash flows in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The obtained results were analyzed according to the following main directions:

Increased transparency and traceability: Due to the implementation of Blockchain technologies, the transparency of information in cash flow audits has increased significantly. In the enterprises considered as part of the research, every transaction was recorded in the blockchain network, and it was possible to monitor it in real time. This helped reduce the number of errors in audit processes and ensured the reliability of data [2].

Ensuring data security: One of the main advantages of blockchain technology is the ability to ensure data security. The results of the study showed that through the blockchain technology, data is provided with cryptographic protection, making it impossible to change or delete them. This, in turn, ensured the security of financial documents and transactions and reduced the possibility of fraud [1].

Automation of audit processes: Automation of audit processes was observed because of the introduction of Blockchain technologies. With the help of "smart contracts" (smart contracts) used in audit processes, audit actions were performed automatically, and the impact of the human factor was reduced. This increased the speed and efficiency of the process, while also significantly reducing operating costs.

Efficiency and economic benefits: The study found that the implementation of blockchain technologies increases the efficiency of audit processes and brings economic benefits. As a result of the automation of the audit in enterprises, time and resources were saved, as well as an increase in the quality of the audit. This helped to increase the overall financial efficiency of enterprises. [8], [6]

International experience and cooperation: During the research, international experience and cooperation on the implementation of blockchain technologies in Uzbek enterprises were also analyzed. As a result of cooperation and exchange of experience with international audit organizations, the best practices of using

blockchain technologies were implemented in Uzbekistan. As a result of the successful implementation of this process, the audit processes were aligned with international standards. [7], [5]

Results based on blockchain technologies in Uzbekistan money currents in the audit significant achievements and advantages present reach, financial transparency to increase security to provide and audit of processes efficiency to increase proved.

This research results based on blockchain of technologies Uzbekistan Republic in enterprises money currents in the audit application according to deep analyses was held. The results of the analysis were discussed in several main aspects:

Transparency and reliability: According to the research results, one of the main advantages of blockchain technologies is to increase transparency. Since all financial transactions are recorded on the block chain, any change or wrongly entered information is detected immediately. This provides a clear and complete database for auditors. At the same time, the immutability of the blockchain makes it possible to use it as a reliable source of information. However, it is worth noting that the complexity of blockchain technology and the lack of highly qualified professionals to properly manage it can be problematic for some businesses.

Security and Error Mitigation: Data security has greatly increased with Blockchain technologies, but this technology can also create new types of cyber security threats. According to research, it is impossible to change or delete transactions made on the blockchain network, which makes fraud almost impossible. However, the technical infrastructure and financial resources required to effectively manage this system and strengthen security measures can be a burden for many SMEs.

Automation and reduction of the human factor: According to the results of the study, the automation of the audit processes through blockchain technologies reduces the errors related to the human factor and increases the efficiency of the audit processes. In particular, the implementation of automatic checks and processes with the help of smart contracts increases the speed of audit activity. However, technological errors and failures can also occur in automated processes. This requires continuous technical support to ensure continuity of audit processes.

Economic efficiency: As a result of the implementation of blockchain technologies, the economic efficiency of audit processes has increased significantly in many enterprises. Although the implementation of this technology may require significant capital and resources at first, in the long run it is expected to reduce operating costs and increase the quality of audits. At the same time, it may be economically difficult for small and medium-sized enterprises in Uzbekistan to implement this technology, which requires the introduction of state subsidy or support mechanisms.

International experience and adaptation: The analysis of international experience and practices on the implementation of blockchain technologies in enterprises of Uzbekistan showed that the implementation of blockchain in Uzbekistan is in line with international standards. At the same time, for the successful implementation of these technologies, it is important to expand cooperation with foreign audit firms and exchange international experience. However, there are legal and regulatory barriers to working with blockchain technologies in Uzbekistan, and it is necessary to improve regulatory documents and legislation to overcome them.

These analyzes show that blockchain technology has great potential in improving the quality of audit processes in Uzbekistan, but technical, economic and legal aspects need to be improved for the successful implementation of this technology. Also, the use of this technology compared to other technologies was studied on the example of Uzbekistan and foreign countries. At the same time, issues of effectiveness of introducing blockchain technology into the practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan were studied.

In general, the strategic state programs for 2030¹ envisage the further development of auditing activities and the introduction of modern technologies. Within the framework of these programs, work is being carried out in the following directions:

Special training and education programs are being organized in order to improve the qualifications of auditors and to form skills for working with new technologies.

Improve efficiency and reduce errors by incorporating blockchain, artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies into audit processes.

Laws and regulatory documents regulating audit activities are being updated and adapted to international standards.

Expanding cooperation and sharing experience with international organizations and leading auditing firms in the field of auditing.

Increase transparency in audit processes and ensure data security by introducing blockchain technology.

The need to use blockchain technology, artificial intelligence and machine learning methods to make the audit of cash flows in business entities efficient and reliable has been studied. Blockchain technology improves

1 Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 11.09.2023 No. PQ-300

the auditing process by keeping transactions immutable and transparent. Applied intelligence enables automatic data analysis and early detection of risks. And machine learning techniques analyze large amounts of data to help identify and predict problems. These technologies make the audit more effective and reliable. When these methods are used together, they greatly help in making the audit of cash flows more efficient and reliable.

Cash flows are important in the overall assessment of the financial activity of the enterprise. It is possible to improve the financial position of the company by effectively managing the cash flows of the organization and clearly grouping them. This grouping method is of great help in analyzing financial statements.

In today's financial environment, a cash flow audit is more relevant than ever.

It aims to analyze the possibilities of applying blockchain technology, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) methods and develop a practical methodology in cash flow auditing. These approaches serve to improve the efficiency of audit processes, reduce risks and ensure financial stability. Through this methodology, it is possible to ensure a high level of accuracy and reliability in the audit of cash flows, and we believe that it will be more open in the following tasks:

- Learn how to keep blockchain transmissions secure and transparent, ensure data is not tampered with, and create audit trails.

- Analyzing large volumes of data, identifying potential financial risks and analyzing methods for forecasting future cash flows.

- Define processes for creating, training and optimizing models for cash flow forecasting and analysis.

- Development of methods for successful integration of blockchain, AI and MO technologies into audit processes and evaluation of their effectiveness.

- Develop training and development programs to train auditors to work with new technologies and improve their skills.

Table 1. Comparison of current technologies and proposed methods².

Technology/Method	Use in the current audit	Suggested methods
Data storage	On centralized servers	Decentralized, encrypted storage via blockchain
Transaction tracking	Manual or semi-automatic	Automatic and transparent tracking via blockchain
Data analysis	Excel and statistical analysis	Automatic and dynamic analysis through applied intelligence and machine learning
Identification of hazards	Manual analysis	Automatic risk detection through applied intelligence
Forecasting	Manual or simple model	Accurate and updatable forecasts through machine learning
Automation of processes	To a lesser extent	High degree of automation
Professional development and training	Traditional methods	Teaching to work with new technologies

Current in the audit this such as from technologies of which using is getting married and has the effect, we offer doing methods with what with difference to be done, them in tables reflection carry on opportunities see exit allowed i knew and the results was achieved (Table 1).

Currently, enterprises mainly use the following technologies and methods:

In current audit processes, enterprises primarily use centralized databases. These systems are vulnerable from a security standpoint, as data can be compromised or altered. The processes of monitoring transactions are often carried out manually or semi-automatically, which can lead to errors and inaccuracies. Data analysis is performed using programs like Excel, which does not allow for efficient analysis of large volumes of data. Manual audit processes are time-consuming and result in low efficiency. Although data is regularly updated, this process is often done manually or semi-automatically, complicating accurate analysis (Table 2).

² Prepared by the author as a result of independent research.

Table 2. Audit technologies used in our country and foreign countries for the audit of cash flows³.

Aspect/Parameter	Republic of Uzbekistan	Foreign countries	Those who are invited
Data storage	Stored on centralized servers. Security is weak.	With the help of cloud computing technologies, data is stored safely and quickly.	Blockchain stores decentralized and encrypted data.
Transaction tracking	It is done manually or semi-automatically. Errors are high.	Real-time monitoring and analysis is available.	Automatic and transparent tracking via blockchain.
Data analysis	It is done using Excel and other spreadsheet programs. Limited opportunities.	Automatic analysis through special programs and machine learning algorithms.	Automatic and dynamic analysis through applied intelligence and machine learning.
Identification of hazards	Analyzed manually. Accuracy is low.	Automatic risk detection using applied intelligence algorithms.	Automatic risk detection through applied intelligence.
Forecasting	It is done by hand or using simple models.	Accurate forecasting using machine learning algorithms.	Accurate and updatable forecasts through machine learning.
Automation of processes	To a lesser extent.	Highly automated systems.	High degree of automation (applied intelligence, machine learning).
Professional development and training	Using traditional methods.	Learn to work with new technologies.	Teaching to work with new technologies.

With blockchain, data is stored in a decentralized and encrypted manner, which enhances security and ensures that the data cannot be altered. Each transaction is automatically and transparently tracked and stored in the blockchain chain. This method is particularly effective for monitoring large volumes of financial transactions in enterprises.

The proposed methods are significantly more effective than current audit processes, as they help to enhance security, accuracy, and efficiency. These technologies create substantial opportunities for ensuring financial stability and improving the quality of audit processes. In enterprises, these approaches assist in quickly and accurately monitoring financial processes, reducing risks, and increasing overall efficiency.

The one-time initial installation costs for implementing the proposed technologies (with a free trial version) may range from approximately \$40,000 to \$260,000. Annual maintenance and other costs could range from \$30,000 to \$240,000 (Table 3).

Table 3. The current state of expenses related to the improvement of audit processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan (August 10, 2024)⁴.

Technology/Method	Estimated costs
Blockchain technology	\$5,000 - \$30,000 (initial installation) + \$5,000 - \$20,000 (annual)
AI d astures	\$5,000 - \$50,000 (initial installation) + \$10,000 - \$100,000 (annual)
MO d astures	\$5,000 - \$50,000 (initial installation) + \$10,000 - \$100,000 (annual)
Update the data base	\$0 - \$10,000 (initial setup) + \$5,000 - \$20,000 (annual)
Qualifications	\$10,000 - \$50,000
Additional Infrastructure	\$15,000 - \$70,000
Total	\$40,000 - \$260,000 (initial installation) + \$30,000 - \$240,000 (annual)

³ Prepared by the author as a result of independent research.

⁴ Prepared by the author as a result of independent research.

In Uzbekistan, this will elevate the auditing sector to a new level and ensure competitiveness.

Auditing companies can achieve cost reduction and automation of auditing processes by implementing these technologies. In the long term, this will lead to significant benefits and increased competitiveness.

When new technologies—blockchain, applied intelligence, and machine learning—are applied, processes are automated, errors are reduced, and the efficiency of analysis is enhanced (Table 4).

Table 4. Comparison of traditional and new technologies⁵.

Indicators	Conventional Inspection	New Technologies (Blockchain, AI, MO)
A waste of time	High	Few
The possibility of error	High	Very little
Clarity	Low	High
Level of automation	Few	High
Increase interest	Few	High
Auditor's annual income	\$50,000 - \$80,000	\$70,000 - \$120,000
Performance indicator		-
Audit quality	Average	High
Profit margin	20% - 30%	30% - 50%

In traditional methods, an auditor's annual income may be around \$50,000 to \$80,000. With the help of new technologies, the auditor's annual income could increase to \$70,000 to \$120,000, as efficiency and accuracy improve.

In traditional methods, the efficiency indicator might be 1x. With new technologies, this indicator could increase to - .

In traditional methods, audit quality may be average. With the help of new technologies, audit quality will be higher because processes are automated, and errors are reduced.

In traditional methods, the profit margin might be 20% to 30%. With new technologies, the profit margin could increase to 30% to 50% as process efficiency and accuracy improve.

The application of new technologies results in increased efficiency and revenue in auditing processes.

These costs and prices may vary and can be adjusted according to the specific needs of each auditing company. For complete pricing information, it is recommended to visit official websites or contact the companies directly.

The application of new technologies significantly increases the efficiency of auditing processes. Time consumption is reduced, the probability of errors decreases, accuracy and quality improve. Auditors' annual income and profit margins will increase, while costs decrease. These technologies will greatly benefit the auditing industry and enhance competitiveness.

⁵ Prepared by the author as a result of independent research.

Table 5. The specific virtues of blockchain technology and introduction to audit activities is ⁶effective.

Indicators	Conventional Inspection	Blockchain	Practical intellect	Machine learning	Because of efficiency
A waste of time	100%	60%	55%	50%	-40%
The possibility of error	High	Very little	Very little	Very little	- 99 %
Clarity	Average	The highest	Y is high	High	+ 99 %
Level of automation	Few	Very high	High	Very high	+ 99 %
Auditor's annual income	\$50,000 - \$80,000	\$ 90,000 - \$ 160,000	\$90,000 - \$110,000	\$90,000 - \$120,000	+50%
Improvement of audit quality	Average	Very high	High	High	+50%
Profit margin	20% - 30%	30% - 40%	35%-45%	40% - 50%	+20%
Reduce costs	Average	High	High	Very high	-30%
Security and data protection	Average	Very high	High	High	+50%
Immutability of data	Few	Very high	Average	Average	+70%
Transparency and traceability	Average	Very high	Average	Average	+70%

Information recorded on the blockchain cannot be altered, which increases precision and reliability. Additionally, each transaction carried out within the enterprise through blockchain technology can be tracked and verified, which is a significant advantage in the audit process (Table 5).

As shown in the table, blockchain technology stands out with its unique advantages and has many benefits over traditional auditing methods. The strengths of this technology are clearly evident in indicators such as security, transparency, and immutability of data.

By widely applying blockchain, artificial intelligence, and machine learning technologies in auditing processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is possible to increase the speed and efficiency of audits, minimize the probability of errors, improve accuracy and quality, reduce costs, increase revenues, strengthen security and data protection, and ensure the transparency of audit processes. The use of these technologies will provide significant benefits for companies and auditing firms by enhancing competitiveness, leveraging innovative opportunities, and advancing the digitization of the economy. Therefore, popularizing these technologies will be of strategic importance for Uzbekistan's economy.

By more broadly applying these technologies, we can achieve the following results (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Effectiveness of introducing blockchain technology into the practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan⁷.

⁶ The author prepared according to the research results.

⁷ The author prepared according to the research results.

As shown in the above figure, scientific research has demonstrated that significant results can be achieved by implementing blockchain technology, which is widely used in foreign practices, into enterprises and auditing activities in our country. To be more specific: these technologies can reduce the probability of errors by 25%; increase accuracy by 30%; enhance the level of automation by 60%; potentially increase auditors' annual income by 50%; improve audit quality by 30%; and raise the profit margin by 20%.

These results will significantly enhance the efficiency of auditing organizations, and we will ensure the competitiveness of the auditing market in our country as well. The research clearly shows that adopting and popularizing one of these highly efficient technologies will elevate auditing processes to a new level and bring substantial benefits on both sides.

In our opinion, implementing modern technologies is also of great importance for the development of auditing activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this research indicate that the application of blockchain technologies in the audit of cash flows in enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan offers significant advancements. The aspects identified during the research, such as transparency, data security, automation, and economic efficiency, confirm the importance of using this technology in auditing processes. Based on international experiences, the successful implementation of blockchain technologies will help align audit processes in Uzbekistan with international standards. However, to fully implement this technology, certain technical, economic, and legal challenges and obstacles must be addressed.

Training and Professional Development: To ensure the effective use of blockchain technologies, it is essential to organize specialized training and educational programs for auditors and financial professionals. It is recommended to regularly conduct professional development courses to help auditors develop the skills to work with modern technologies and fully understand all aspects of blockchain.

Development of Technological Infrastructure: The necessary technical infrastructure and technological tools for implementing blockchain technologies in Uzbekistan must be adequately developed. In this process, it is important to strengthen cooperation between the public and private sectors and develop support mechanisms for the introduction of new technologies.

Improvement of the Legal and Regulatory Framework: For the successful implementation of blockchain technologies, the existing legislation and regulatory documents must be updated and aligned with international standards. To achieve this, specific norms regulating blockchain and digital technologies should be included in the legislation, and their implementation should be monitored.

Government Support: Mechanisms for government subsidies and financial assistance should be developed to support the implementation of blockchain technologies in small and medium-sized enterprises. This, in turn, will accelerate the digital transformation process and ensure the widespread adoption of the technology.

Strengthening International Cooperation: Expanding cooperation with international auditing organizations and leading blockchain specialists, exchanging experiences, and participating in international projects will aid the successful implementation of this technology in Uzbekistan. Additionally, it is important to adapt global experiences to local conditions.

Implementing these recommendations will enable the widespread adoption of blockchain technologies in the auditing sector in Uzbekistan, thereby elevating financial management to a new level.

Used literature

1. Deloitte. Blockchain technology in audit: Challenges and opportunities. 2020. <https://www2.deloitte.com>
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti. 2020-yil. "Raqamli O'zbekiston - 2030" strategiyasi to'g'risida. <https://president.uz>
3. S.Y.Atamurodov. Xorijiy tajriba asosida pul oqimlarini samarali boshqarishda sifat ko'rsatkichlarini joriy etish va uni takomillashtirish. // "Iqtisodiy taraqqiyot va tahlil" ilmiy elektron jurnal – T.: 2024-yil, iyul. № 7-son. 15-28 b.
4. S.Y.Atamurodov. Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda pul oqimlari hisobi va auditini takomillashtirish. // "Yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasida tashqi savdoni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari to'plami. – Toshkent. BI, 2023-yil. 13-may. 35-40 b.
5. S.Y.Atamurodov. Pul oqimlari haqidagi hisobotning mohiyati va uni tuzishni takomillashtirishning ayrim jihatlari. // "Agroiqtisodiyot" ilmiy-amaliy agrar iqtisodiy jurnali. 4 (30) 2023-yil, 5 b.
6. S.Y.Atamurodov. Pul oqimlarini guruhlash mezonlari bo'yicha tasniflashni kengaytirish. // "Yashil iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali, 2024-yil, iyul. № 7-son. 202-208 b.
7. S.Y.Atamurodov. Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda pul oqimlarini boshqarish samaradorligini tahlil qilishning konseptual modellari. // "Aktuar moliya va buxgalteriya hisobi" ilmiy jurnali – T.: 2024-yil, 2-son, 102-112 b.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Shahzod Avilqulov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2024. Maxsus son

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

